

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYTICAL EQUATIONS OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF LIQUID HYDROCARBONS

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Abstract

Using data on the thermal conductivity of some saturated hydrocarbons, obtained by the author on an experimental installation operating according to a non-stationary method, as well as experimental data from other scientists, equations are proposed for calculating the thermal conductivity of saturated hydrocarbons. These equations can be applied to other substances as well. Expressions are proposed based on some theoretical models that are in good agreement with the experimental data.

Keywords: saturated hydrocarbons, thermal conductivity, heat capacity, molecular weight.

Experimental determination of the thermal conductivity of liquids is a laborious problem. Therefore, the use of various functional dependencies and theoretical equations is of particular interest.

The accumulated amount of experimental data on the thermal conductivity of liquid saturated hydrocarbons at various temperatures allows them to be generalized. Many works have been and are being carried out in this direction [1, p. 267-271; 2, p. 2968-2977; 3, p. 106566]. Based on the data obtained by the author himself, a generalization of these data was carried out using some theoretical models.

At present, a number of formulas are known for calculating the thermal conductivity of liquids.

The theoretical concept of the mechanism of heat propagation in liquids as the transfer of energy through elastic vibrations was used by N.B. Vargaftik [3, p. 13] to describe experimental data on the thermal conductivity of various liquids. Based on this theory, a formula for the thermal conductivity coefficient of the following form was obtained:

$$\lambda = AC_p \left(\frac{\rho}{M} \right)^{\frac{4}{3}}, \quad (1)$$

where C_p is the heat capacity of the liquid at constant pressure; ρ is the density of the liquid; M is the molecular weight.

The coefficient A , which is proportional to the velocity of propagation of elastic waves in a liquid, depends on the type of substance and temperature.

Usage of (1) requires knowledge of the quantities A , M , as well as C_p and ρ .

To find C_p of saturated hydrocarbons at temperatures $T_1 = 0.5T_{cr}$, the following relationship can be used:

$$C_p = C_1 + 0.086M(M - a) \frac{T - T_1}{L}, \quad (2)$$

where a is the molecular weight of the group CH_2 ($a=14$).

If we represent the dependence of C and M graphically (fig. 1), then it will be seen that for the case of higher hydrocarbons, starting with n.pentane, it has a rectilinear form.

Based on experimental data on thermal conductivity of n. butane, pentane, hexane, heptane and octane [4, p. 232-234] the character of the change in the coefficient A , which decreases with increasing temperature for all hydrocarbons, is determined. The higher the molecular weight, the greater this decrease. The value of A at a temperature

$T_1 = 0.5T_{cr}$ for saturated hydrocarbons is not the same, it increases with increasing molecular weight, but at $T=T_{cr}$ it is almost the same.

Fig.1

This dependence can be expressed with great accuracy by the following empirical formula

$$A = A_b - B(T - T_b)\Delta t_0^3 \sqrt{\frac{T_1}{T}}, \quad (3)$$

where A_b is the value of A at the boiling point. B is a constant.

The value $\Delta t_0 = T_{cr} - T_b$ increases monotonically with increasing M .

Comparison of the thermal conductivity values obtained by equations (1)-(3) for the methane series with the experimental ones showed a maximum discrepancy of 2%.

The value of thermal conductivity for a class of substances is conveniently expressed as the sum of two terms, so that the first term does not depend on the molecular weight, but depends only on the reduced temperature. The second term depends both on M and T . The dependence of both terms on T is the same.

Therefore

$$\lambda = \lambda' + \lambda'' \quad (4)$$

Here

$$\lambda' = bf(\tau), \quad (5)$$

$$\lambda'' = n\varphi(\tau, M) = nf(\tau)\varphi'(M). \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) can be represented as follows:

$$\lambda' = \lambda_1' \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_1}(\tau), \quad (7)$$

where λ_1' is the value of λ' at T_l .

λ'' at constant τ will unambiguously depend on the molecular weight.

If we represent λ at $\tau = 1$ for hydrocarbons according to the experimental data calculated by (1) depending on the molecular weight, we will obtain a

curve (Fig. 2) which passes through a minimum, and then, with an increase in M , asymptotically approaches a certain value, that in the equation (7) corresponds to λ_1' .

According to the graph, for heavier hydrocarbons at constant thermal conductivities, they are equal to $\lambda'' \approx 0$, i.e. $\lambda \approx \lambda'$.

This behavior of thermal conductivity is apparently inherent not only to the class of saturated hydrocarbons. In the same figure 2, the curves for normal alcohols and aromatic hydrocarbons at $\tau = 1$ clearly indicate a tendency for the thermal conductivity to pass through a minimum, and subsequently to its asymptotic approximation to the value of λ_1' .

If you report from the line corresponding to the value λ_1' , then the resulting value λ will be identical to the value λ_1'' . Increasing or decreasing the value τ within the temperature range from T_b to $0.8T_{cr}$ does not affect the shape of the curves, but decreases or increases their amplitude accordingly.

Dependence curves (7) are analytically expressed by the following empirical equations:

For the case $M \leq 41.2$

$$\lambda'' = B \left(11.2 \cdot e^{\frac{M}{96.2}} - 7.32 \right), \quad (8)$$

For $M \geq 41.2$

$$\lambda'' = B \left[0.698 \cdot e^{8.6 \left(1 - \frac{M}{50} \right) - \left(\frac{50}{M} \right)^6} \right], \quad (9)$$

where B is a constant value for a given.

Fig.1

When $\tau = 1$ $B = 464 \cdot 10^{-7}$ and in general

$$B = 464 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_1} (\tau) \eta(M) .$$

Equation (5) can also be written in another form:

$$\lambda = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_1} (\tau) [\lambda_1' + \lambda_1''] = \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_1} (\tau) \eta(M), \quad (10)$$

where $\eta(M)$ is a function that uniquely depends on the molecular weight for a given class of substances, and $\eta(M)$ at $\tau = 1$ is equal to λ .

References

1. Emad Talib Hashim & Iamir E. Maloka. Thermal-Conductivity of Liquid Hydrocarbons. Petroleum Science and Technology Journal. 2005. Vol. 23: 3-4, Ps. 267-271, DOI: 10.1081/LFT-200028289

2. Xiufang Zhao, Xian Wang, Yanxing Zhao, Xueqiang Dong, Yunxiao Wang and Maoqiong Gong. Prediction of the Thermal Conductivity for Liquid Hydrocarbons and Halogenated Hydrocarbons. American Chemical Society. Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research Journal. 2023. Vol. 62 (6), Ps. 2968–2977, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.2c03793>

3. Xiong Zheng, Yanqiong Bao, Dan Qu, Jing Wu, Guangzhao Qin, Yu Liu. Thermal conductivity measurements for long-chain n-alkanes at evaluated temperature and pressure: n-dodecane and n-tetradecane. The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics. 2021. Volume 162, P. 106566, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jct.2021.106566>

4. Коротких А.Г. Теплопроводность материалов: учебное пособие. Томский политехнический университет. Томск: Изд-во Томского политехнического университета. 2011. 97с.

5. Назиев Д.Я. Теплопроводность углеводородов и методы ее измерения. Монография. Баку. Азербайджан. 2001. - 357 с.